

Collateral Posting Framework

Tim Xiao

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a framework for calculating credit exposure under collateral posting. We empirically gauge the impact of collateral agreements on risk measurements. Our findings show that collateral posting can reduce credit risk and credit valuation adjustment (CVA). The results also suggest a negative correlation between collateralization and CVA as an increase in collateralization causes a decrease in CVA charge and vice-versa. These findings improve our understanding of the relationship between collateralization and CVA.

Key words: collateralization, asset pricing, swap premium spread, credit valuation adjustment, value at risk

Collateralization is a critical component of the plumbing of the financial system. The use of collateral in financial markets has increased sharply over the past decade, yet analytical and empirical research on collateralization is relatively sparse. The effect of collateralization on valuation and risk is an understudied area.

Contrary to previous studies, we present a model that characterizes a collateral process directly based on the fundamental principal and legal structure of CSA. The model is devised that allows for collateralization adhering to bankruptcy laws. As such, it can back out price changes due to counterparty risk and collateral posting. Our model is very useful for valuing off-the-run or outstanding derivatives.

Interest rate swaps collectively account for two-thirds of all outstanding derivatives. An ISDA mid-market swap rate is based on a mid-day polling. Dealers use this market rate as a reference and make some adjustments to quote an actual swap rate. The adjustment or swap premium is determined by many factors, such as credit risk, liquidity risk, funding cost, operational cost and expected profit, etc.

Unfortunately, we do not know the detailed allocation of a swap premium, i.e., what percentage of the adjustment is charged for each factor. Thus, a direct empirical assessment of the impact of collateralization on swap rate is impossible.

Empirically, we obtain a unique proprietary dataset from an investment bank. We use these data and a statistical measurement R^2 to examine whether credit risk and collateralization, alone or in combination, are sufficient to explain market swap premium spreads. We first study the marginal impact of credit risk. Since credit default swap (CDS) premium theoretically reflects the credit risk of a firm, we use the market swap premium spreads as the response variable and the CDS premium differences between two counterparties as the explanatory variable. The estimation result shows that the adjusted R^2 is 0.7472, implying that approximately 75% of market spreads can be explained by counterparty credit risk. In other words, counterparty risk alone can provide a good but not overwhelming prediction on spreads.

Second, how does collateralization affect counterparty credit risk? Credit value adjustment (CVA) is the most prominent measurement in counterparty credit risk. We select all the CSA counterparty

portfolios in the dataset and then compute their CVAs. We find that the CVA of a collateralized counterparty portfolio is always smaller than the one of the same portfolio without collateralization. We also find that credit risk is negatively correlated with collateralization as an increase in collateralization causes a decrease in credit risk. The empirical tests corroborate our theoretical conclusions that collateralization can reduce CVA charges and mitigate counterparty risk.

The rest of this article is organized as follows: First we present a new model for pricing collateralized financial derivatives. Then we discuss empirical evidences. Finally, the conclusions and discussion are provided. All proofs and detailed derivations are contained in the appendices.

Pricing Collateralized Financial Derivatives

There are three types of collateralization: partial, over or full. A positive effective threshold corresponds to partial-collateralization where the posting of collateral is less than the MTM value. A negative effective threshold represents over-collateralization where the posting of collateral is greater than the MTM value. A zero-value effective threshold equates with full-collateralization where the posting of collateral is equal to the MTM value. Our generic model is applicable to all the types.

We consider a filtered probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{P})$ satisfying the usual conditions, where Ω denotes a sample space, \mathcal{F} denotes a σ -algebra, \mathcal{P} denotes a probability measure, and $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ denotes a filtration. In the reduced-form framework, the stopping or default time τ of a firm is modeled as a Cox arrival process whose first jump occurs at default and is defined by,

$$\tau = \inf \left\{ t : \int_0^t h(s, \Gamma_s) ds \geq \Delta \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $h(t)$ or $h(t, \Gamma_t)$ denotes the stochastic hazard rate dependent on an exogenous common state Γ_t , and Δ is a unit exponential random variable independent of Γ_t .

It is well-known that the survival probability from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$p(t, s) := P(\tau > s | \tau > t) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (2a)$$

The default probability for the period (t, s) is given by

$$q(t, s) := P(\tau \leq s | \tau > t) = 1 - p(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (2b)$$

Let valuation date be t . Consider a financial contract that promises to pay a $X_T > 0$ at maturity date $T > t$, and nothing before the time.

The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. For a discrete one-payment period (t, T) economy, at time T the contract either defaults with the default probability $q(t, T)$ or survives with the survival probability $p(t, T)$. The survival payoff is equal to X_T and the default payoff is a fraction of X_T : φX_T , where φ is the recovery rate. The value of this defaultable contract at time t is the discounted expectation of all the possible payoffs and is given by

$$V^N(t) = E\{D(t, T)[p(t, T) + \varphi(T)q(t, T)]X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} = E[D(t, T)I(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (3)$$

where $E\{\bullet | \mathcal{F}_t\}$ is the expectation conditional on \mathcal{F}_t , $D(t, T)$ denotes the risk-free discount factor at time t for maturity T and $I(t, T) = [p(t, T) + \varphi(T)q(t, T)]$ can be regarded as a risk-adjusted discount ratio.

Suppose that there is a CSA agreement between a bank and a counterparty in which the counterparty is required to deliver collateral when the mark-to-market (MTM) value arises over the effective threshold H .

The choice of modeling assumptions for collateralization should be based on the legal structure of CSA. According to the Bankruptcy Law, if the demand for default payment exceeds the collateral value, the balance of the demand will be treated as an unsecured claim and subject to its pro rate distribution under the Bankruptcy Code's priority scheme (see Garlson [1992], Routh and Douglas [2005], and Edwards and Morrison [2005]). The default payment under a CSA can be mathematically expressed as

$$P^D(T) = C(T) + \varphi(T)(X_T - C(T)) = \varphi(T)X_T + C(T)(1 - \varphi(T)) \quad (4)$$

where $C(T)$ is the collateral amount at T .

According to CSA, if the contract value $V^C(t)$ is less than the effective threshold $H(t)$, no collateral is posted; otherwise, the required collateral is equal to the difference between the contract value and the effective threshold. The collateral amount posted at time t can be expressed mathematically as

$$C(t) = \max(V^C(t) - H(t), 0) \quad (5)$$

where $H(t) = 0$ corresponds to full-collateralization; $H(t) > 0$ represents partial-collateralization; and $H(t) < 0$ reflects over-collateralization.

The value of the CSA contract is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$V^C(t) = E\{D(t, T)[q(t, T)(C(T) + \varphi(T)(X_T - C(T))) + p(t, T)X_T] | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (6)$$

After some simple mathematics, we have the following proposition

Proposition 1: *The value of a collateralized single-payment contract is given by*

$$V^C(t) = E[F(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] - G(t, T) \quad (7a)$$

where

$$F(t, T) = (1_{V^N(t) \leq H(t)} + 1_{V^N(t) > H(t)} / \bar{I}(t, T)) I(t, T) D(t, T) \quad (7b)$$

$$G(t, T) = 1_{V^N(t) > H(t)} H(t) \bar{q}(t, T) (1 - \varphi(T)) / \bar{I}(t, T) \quad (7c)$$

where $\bar{I}(t, T) = E(I(t, T) | \mathcal{F}_t)$, $I(t, T)$ and $V^N(t)$ are defined in (3).

The pricing in Proposition 1 is relatively straightforward. We first compute $V^N(t)$ and then test whether its value is greater than $H(t)$. After that, the calculations of $F(t, T)$, $G(t, T)$ and $V^C(t)$ are easily obtained.

We discuss a special case where $H(t) = 0$ corresponding to full-collateralization. Suppose that default probabilities are uncorrelated with interest rates and payoffs¹. From Proposition 1, we can easily obtain $V^C(t) = V^F(t)$ where $V^F(t) = E[D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t]$ is the risk-free value. That is to say: the value of a fully-collateralized contract is equal to the risk-free value. This conclusion is in line with the results of Johannes and Sundareshan [2007], Fujii and Takahashi [2012], and Piterbarg [2010].

Proposition 2: *The value of a collateralized multiple-payment contract is given by*

$$V^C(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (F(T_j, T_{j+1})) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t \right] - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} E \left[\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (F(T_j, T_{j+1})) G(T_i, T_{i+1}) | \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (8a)$$

where

$$F(T_j, T_{j+1}) = \left(1_{J(T_j, T_{j+1}) \leq H(T_j)} + 1_{J(T_j, T_{j+1}) > H(T_j)} / \bar{I}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) I(T_j, T_{j+1}) D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \quad (8b)$$

$$G(T_j, T_{j+1}) = 1_{J(T_j, T_{j+1}) > H(T_j)} H(T_j) \bar{q}(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi(T_{j+1})) / \bar{I}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \quad (8c)$$

$$J(T_j, T_{j+1}) = E \left[D(T_j, T_{j+1}) I(T_j, T_{j+1}) (V^C(T_{j+1}) + X_{j+1}) | \mathcal{F}_{T_j} \right] \quad (8d)$$

where $\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} F(T_j, T_{j+1}) = 1$ is an empty product when $i = 0$. Empty product allows for a much shorter mathematical presentation of many subjects.

Empirical Results

Due to a close relationship, any statistical software that performs linear regression analysis will outputs R^2 value. Thus, conveniently we report R^2 together with other regression results that may provide additional statistical and financial insights.

¹ Moody's Investor's Service [2000] presents statistics that suggest that the correlations between interest rates, default probabilities and recovery rates are very small and provides a reasonable comfort level for the uncorrelated assumption.

Unlike the generic benchmark swap rates, swap premia are determined according to the basic principles of supply and demand. The swap market is highly competitive. In a competitive market, prices are determined by the impersonal forces of demand and supply, but not by the manipulations of powerful buyers or sellers.

In contrast to previous research, this subsection mainly studies swap adjustments/premia related to credit risk and collateralization. It empirically measures the effect of collateralization on pricing and compares it with model-implied prices.

To circumvent this difficulty, we design an indirect verification process in which we select some CSA swap pairs such that the two contracts in each pair have exactly the same terms and conditions but are traded with different counterparties under different collateral agreements. It is reasonable to believe that the difference between the two contracts in each pair is solely attributed to collateralized counterparty credit risk, as all the other risks/costs are identical. Therefore, by accounting for credit risk and collateralization, we can efficiently compare the implied spreads with the market spreads for these pairs.

Exhibit 1: A pair of 20-year swap contracts

This exhibit displays the terms and conditions of two swap contracts that have different counterparties but are otherwise the same. We hide the counterparty names according to the security policy of the investment bank while everything else is authentic.

	Swap 1		Swap 2	
	Fixed leg	Floating leg	Fixed leg	Floating leg
Counterparty	X		Y	
Effective date	15/09/2005	15/09/2005	15/09/2005	15/09/2005
Maturity date	15/09/2025	15/09/2025	15/09/2025	15/09/2025
Day count	30/360	ACT/360	30/360	ACT/360
Payment frequency	Semi-annually	Quarterly	Semi-annually	Quarterly
Swap rate	4.9042%	-	4.9053%	-

Roll over	Mod_follow	Mod_follow	Mod_follow	Mod_follow
Principal	25,000,000	25,000,000	25,000,000	25,000,000
Currency	USD	USD	USD	USD
Pay/receive	Bank receives	Party X receives	Bank receives	Party Y receives
Floating index	-	3 month LIBOR	-	3 month LIBOR
Floating spread	-	0	-	0
Floating reset	-	Quarterly	-	Quarterly

An interest rate curve is the term structure of interest rates, derived from observed market instruments that represent the most liquid and dominant interest rate products for certain time horizons. Normally the curve is divided into three parts. The short end of the term structure is determined using LIBOR rates. The middle part of the curve is constructed using Eurodollar futures. The far end is derived using mid swap rates. The LIBOR-future-swap curve is presented in Exhibit 2. After bootstrapping the curve, we get the continuously compounded zero rates.

Exhibit 2: USD LIBOR-future-swap curve

This exhibit displays the closing mid prices as of September 15, 2005

Instrument Name	Price
September 21 2005 LIBOR	3.6067%
September 2005 Eurodollar 3 month	96.1050
December 2005 Eurodollar 3 month	95.9100
March 2006 Eurodollar 3 month	95.8100
June 2006 Eurodollar 3 month	95.7500
September 2006 Eurodollar 3 month	95.7150
December 2006 Eurodollar 3 month	95.6800
2 year swap rate	4.2778%

3 year swap rate	4.3327%
4 year swap rate	4.3770%
5 year swap rate	4.4213%
6 year swap rate	4.4679%
7 year swap rate	4.5120%
8 year swap rate	4.5561%
9 year swap rate	4.5952%
10 year swap rate	4.6368%
12 year swap rate	4.7089%
15 year swap rate	4.7957%
20 year swap rate	4.8771%
25 year swap rate	4.9135%

According to Proposition 2, we also need counterparty-related information, such as recovery rates, hazard rates and collateral thresholds. The CDS premia and recovery rates are given in Exhibit 3 and the collateral thresholds and MTAs of the CSA agreements are displayed in Exhibit 4. We can compute the hazard rates via a standard calibration process (see J.P. Morgan [2001]).

Exhibit 3: CDS premia and recovery rates

This exhibit displays the closing CDS premia as of September 15, 2005 and recovery rates

Counterparty name	Bank	Company X	Company Y
6 month CDS spread	0.00031	0.000489	0.000808
1 year CDS spread	0.000333	0.00056	0.001017
2 year CDS spread	0.000516	0.000866	0.00154
3 year CDS spread	0.000664	0.001147	0.002114
4 year CDS spread	0.000848	0.00147	0.002768
5 year CDS spread	0.001012	0.001783	0.003439

7 year CDS spread	0.001334	0.002289	0.004283
10 year CDS spread	0.001727	0.002952	0.005281
15 year CDS spread	0.001907	0.003283	0.005814
20 year CDS spread	0.002023	0.003266	0.006064
30 year CDS spread	0.002021	0.00336	0.006461
Recovery rate	0.39213	0.35847	0.33872

Exhibit 4: CSA agreement

This exhibit provides the collateral thresholds and MTAs under the CSA agreements.

CSA agreement	1		2	
	Bank	Company X	Bank	Company Y
Counterparty name	Bank	Company X	Bank	Company Y
Threshold	0	0	0	0
MTA	500000	500000	500000	500000

Given the above information, we are able to compute the collateralized swap rates. We first use the LMM to evolve the interest rates and then determine the associated CSA-adjusted discount factors as well as the cost of bearing unsecured credit risk according to Proposition 2. Finally, we calculate the collateralized swap rates via a backward induction method. The results are given in Exhibit 5.

Exhibit 5: Swap rate results

This exhibit presents the model-implied swap rates and premia as well as the dealer-quoted market swap rates and premia, where Swap premium (in bps) = Swap rate – Generic swap rate, and Premium spread = Premium of swap 2 – Premium of swap 1.

	Swap 1		Swap 2		Premium spread	Generic swap rate
	Swap rate	Premium	Swap rate	Premium		

Model-implied	0.048780	0.09 bps	0.048790	0.19 bps	0.10 bps	0.048771
Dealer quoted	0.049042	2.71 bps	0.049053	2.82 bps	0.11 bps	

By accounting for both credit risk and collateralization, we calculate the model-implied swap rates as 0.048780 and 0.048790 shown in Exhibit 5. Consequently, the model-implied swap premia are 0.09 bps and 0.19 bps. The results imply that only a small portion of a swap premium is attributed to unsecured credit risk. Intuitively the small impact of credit risk and collateral posting on a swap premium is mainly due to 1) only the swap coupons rather than the notional amount are exposed to counterparty risk; 2) the initial swap rate sets the contract value close to zero and there is only 50% chance to develop counterparty risk; 3) collateralization mitigates credit risk. This would certainly not be the case for other derivatives. The result is in line with the findings of Duffie and Huang [1996], Duffie and Singleton [1999], and Minton [1997].

Repeating this exercise for the remaining pairs, we find that the model-implied spreads fluctuate randomly around the market spreads. We refer to the differences between the model-implied premium spreads and the market quoted premium spreads as the *model-market premium spread differentials*. The summary statistics of the market spreads, the model-implied spreads, and the model-market spread differentials are presented in Exhibit 6. It shows that the average of the model-market spread differentials is only -0.03 bps, which can be partly attributed to noise. The results indicate prima facie that the model performs quite well. The empirical tests corroborate the theoretical prediction on premium spreads.

Exhibit 6: Summary statistics of model-implied swap premium spreads, market swap premium spreads and model-market swap premium spread differentials

All values are displayed in bps. Model-market swap premium spread differential = Model-implied swap premium spread – Market-quoted swap premium spread.

	Max	Min	Mean	Median	Std
Market quoted swap premium spreads	3.08	-5.25	-0.46	-0.15	1.80

Model-implied swap premium spreads	2.10	-5.33	-0.44	0.03	1.73
Model-market premium spread differentials	0.99	-1.18	-0.03	0.05	0.46

The results of this regression are shown in Exhibit 7. It can be seen that the adjusted R^2 is 0.7472, implying that approximately 74% of market premium spreads can be explained by credit risk alone. We provide empirical evidence that counterparty credit risk alone plays a significant but not overwhelming role in determining credit-related spreads when contracts are under collateral agreements. Moreover, the slope is 0.0127, suggesting that a CDS spread of about 100 bps translates into a swap spread of about 1.27 bps. Finally the small p-value indicates that the changes in CDS premia are closely related to the changes in market premium spreads.

Exhibit 7: Marginal credit risk regression results

This exhibit presents the regression results for the following regression model:

$$\text{MarketSwapPremiumSpreads} = a + b * \text{DifferencesBetweenCounterpartyCDSs} + \varepsilon$$

where the market swap premium spreads are used as the dependent variable and the differences between the counterparty CDS premia as the explanatory variable.

Slope	Intercept	Adjusted R^2	Significance F	T value	P value
0.0127	-2.7E-04	0.7472	1.1E-05	18.6	1.51E-66

According to ISDA Margin Survey (ISDA [2013]), 73.7% of OTC derivatives are subject to collateral agreements. For large firms, the figure is 80.7%. Accounting for collateralization has become increasingly important in pricing OTC derivatives. Since the implied spreads generated by our model take into account both credit risk and collateralization, the statistical relationship between the market spreads and the model-implied spreads should refer to the joint effect of counterparty credit risk and

collateralization on market spreads. Thus, we present another regression model where the market spreads are regressed on the implied spreads. The regression results are shown in Exhibit 8.

Exhibit 8: Credit risk and collateralization combined regression results

This exhibit presents the regression results for the following regression model:

$$\text{MarketSwapPremiumSpreads} = a + b * \text{ImpliedSwapPremiumSpreads} + \varepsilon$$

where the market swap premium spreads are used as the dependent variable and the model-implied swap premium spreads as the explanatory variable.

Slope	Intercept	Adjusted R^2	Significance F	T value	P value
0.9857	4.48E-05	0.9906	3.21E-08	25.4	3.16E-110

The empirical results shed light on the economic and statistical significance of collateralization. The increase in the explanatory power of swap premium spreads bears an interesting finding: It seems that credit risk alone has a modest explanatory power on premium spreads. Only the combination of credit risk and collateralization can sufficiently explain them.

Impact of collateralization on credit risk

From the same dataset above, we find that there are a total of 3052 counterparties having live trades as of May 11, 2012. 516 of them have CSA agreements. We randomly select one counterparty portfolio that contains 476 interest rate swaps, 36 interest rate swaptions and 223 interest rate caps/floors. First, we compute the risk-free value $V^F = 2,737,702$ that is relatively straightforward as the risk-free portfolio value is what trading systems or pricing models normally report.

Next, we further assume that there is a CSA agreement in which the threshold is 2 million and the MTA is 100,000. The risky value of the portfolio is calculated as $V^C = 2,725,094$ according to

Proposition 2. The CVA with collateralization is given by $CVA_c = V^F - V^C = 12,608$. Similarly, we can compute the CVAs under different collateral arrangements and present the results in Exhibit 9.

Exhibit 9. Impact of Collateralization on CVA

This exhibit shows that CVA increases with collateral threshold. The infinite collateral threshold is equivalent to no collateral agreement and the zero-value collateral threshold corresponds to full collateralization. An increase in collateral threshold leads to a decrease in collateralization.

Effective Threshold	0	2.1 Million	4.1 Million	6.1 Million	8.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
CVA	0	12,608	23,685	33,504	42,254	49,688

We extend our analysis to other CSA portfolios. The results hold across different CSA counterparties and collateral agreements. Our findings show that collateral posting can reduce credit risk and CVA. The results also suggest a negative correlation between collateralization and CVA as an increase in collateralization causes a decrease in CVA charge and vice-versa. These findings improve our understanding of the relationship between collateralization and CVA.

Impact of collateralization on market risk

There are three commonly used methodologies to calculate VaR – parametric, historical simulation and Monte Carlo simulation. Parametric model estimates VaR directly from the standard deviation of portfolio returns typically assuming returns are normally distributed. Historical simulation calculates VaR from the distribution of actual historical returns. Whilst Monte Carlo simulation computes VaR from a distribution constructed from random outcomes. In this paper, we calculate historical VaR.

First, we compute the VaR of the sub-portfolio without considering credit risk. The calculated result as of May 11, 2012 is -386,570. Here the VaR is a negative value by definition. However, the industry convention is to report VaR as a positive number that is the amount of money one can lose. Thus, people

in the market usually say that the VaR is 386,570 in this case. This convention can be confusing in places. If one says that VaR increases, the numbers actually become smaller or move into the left tail.

However, market risk and credit risk actually reinforce each other. Default-induced credit losses can be driven by market price changes. At the same time, the changes in prices depend on the rating migration or increase in the default perception of the firm. The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (see BCBS [2009]) also finds that those banks that were more severely affected in the global financial crisis measured their market and credit risk separately, whereas banks that used an integrated approach to market and credit risk measurement were much less impacted. Measuring market risk without considering credit risk may mask the significant impact of credit risk and often leads to underestimation of risk.

Next, we measure VaR again by considering both counterparty credit risk and collateralization. Assume that there is a CSA arrangement. The VaR values under different effective collateral thresholds are displayed in Exhibit 10.

Exhibit 10. Impact of Collateralization on VaR

This exhibit shows that VaR increases with collateral threshold. The infinite collateral threshold is equivalent to no collateral agreement and the zero-value collateral threshold corresponds to full collateralization.

Effective Threshold	0	2.1 Million	4.1 Million	6.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
VaR	-386,570	-398,235	-404,401	-410,756	-418,950

Our findings suggest that there are important interactions between market and credit risk. We find a positive correlation between market and credit risk as they increase or decrease together. We also find that collateralization is actually negatively correlated with market risk, i.e., an increase in collateralization causes a drop in market risk. Said differently, collateral posting can reduce market risk. Our research contributes to the understanding of the interaction between market and credit risk.

Conclusion

Empirically, we use a unique proprietary dataset to measure the effect of collateralization on pricing and compare it with model-implied prices. The empirical results show that the model-implied prices are quite close to the market-quoted prices, suggesting that the model is fairly accurate on pricing collateralized derivatives.

We also find evidence that there is a strong linkage between market and credit risk. Our research results suggest that banks and regulators need to think about an integrated framework to capture material interactions of these two types of risk. This requires all profits and losses are gauged in a consistent way across risk types as they tend to be driven by the same economic factors. Our finding leads to an improved understanding of the interaction between market and credit risk and how this interaction is related to risk measurement and management.

References

- Collin-Dufresne, P. and Solnik, B. "On the term structure of default premia in the swap and LIBOR markets." *Journal of Finance* 56 (2001), pp.1095-1115.
- Duffie, D., and K.J. Singleton, K.J. "Modeling term structure of defaultable bonds." *Review of Financial Studies*, 12(1999), pp. 687-720.
- Feldhutter, P. and Lando, D. "Decomposing swap spreads. *Journal of Financial Economics*," 88 (2008), pp. 375-405.
- FinPricing, 2017, Valuation, <https://finpricing.com/lib/EqBarrier.html>
- Fujii, M. and Takahashi, A. "Collateralized credit default swaps and default dependence: Implications for the central counterparties." *Journal of Credit Risk*, 8(2012), pp. 1-10.

Grinblatt, M., "An analytic solution for interest rate swap spreads." *Review of International Finance*, 2 (2001), pp. 113-149.

ISDA. "ISDA margin survey 2013." 2013

J.P. Morgan, "Par credit default swap spread approximation from default probabilities." 2001.

Minton, B. "An Empirical Examination of Basic Valuation Models for Plain Vanilla U.S. Interest Rate Swaps." *Journal of Financial Economics*, 44 (1997), pp. 251-277.

Piterbarg, V. "Funding beyond discounting: collateral agreements and derivatives pricing." *Risk Magazine*, 2010 (2010), pp. 97-102.

Sorensen, E. and Bollier, T. "Pricing swap default risk." *Financial Analysts Journal*, 50 (1994), pp. 23-33.

Xiao, T. "An accurate solution for credit value adjustment (CVA) and wrong way risk." *Journal of Fixed Income*, 25 (2015), pp. 84-95.